

PreMETS

**Predictive Maintenance Education & Training System:
An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in
Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial
cooperation, education, and training**

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D7.9 Impact Assessment Plan

Draft

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Abbreviations and Terminology

Abbreviations	
EC	European Commission
IAP	Impact Assessment Plan
WP	Work Package

Terminology	
Evaluation	<u>Systematic collection and analysis of information</u> on the actual performance of a project. Its aim is to analyse the relevance, progress, success, and cost-effectiveness of the project. An evaluation compares planned results with the actual results of a project. It is a diagnostic tool. MID project and FINAL project
Monitoring	<u>Continuing management exercise</u> . When implementing a project, monitoring deals exclusively with the conversion of inputs into outputs. This exercise will help evaluate if what was supposed to be done really is. Adjustments to the project are possible when monitoring is done throughout the project management life cycle.
Performance measures	Indicators that provide information (either quantitative or qualitative) on the extent to which the results of a project have been achieved. Evaluation is often confused with measures used to evaluate. Any activity which aims at interpreting results, or data obtained from measures, are part of an evaluation. To assure that the evaluation process leads to good decision-making, it must rest on correct and precise measures.
Qualitative measuring	Aims at collecting data to describe and evaluate a situation or an activity. Qualitative measuring tends to be more anecdotal. Case studies are a good example.
Quantitative measuring	Aims at collecting data to measure (through numbers and statistics) the range or the scope of an activity . Examples of quantitative measures include the number of end users in a project, their age or education level. Quantitative measures may be obtained through surveys.
Efficiency	Refers to producing planned outputs within budgetary limits and established deadlines. For example: Was the implementation of the project professionally managed?
Effectiveness	Refers to achieving planned results and contributing to attain established goals and objectives. For example: To what extent were the project's objectives achieved?
Impact	A general statement of desired outcomes to be achieved over a specified period (the reasons for which the National Agency wishes to undertake the project).

Executive Summary

This document presents the Impact Assessment Plan of PreMETS. It will be a living document reviewed and updated throughout the whole duration of the project up to M36.

The main objective of Deliverable 7.9 is to establish a set of indicators which need to be measured over time in order to assess the impact of PreMETS solution in the medium-long term across different dimensions. The impact assessment results need to be considered, monitored and re-measured iteratively to maintain an overview on the impact of the solution. The Impact Assessment Plan will be further developed over the life cycle of the project and the main indicators are to be measured through qualitative and quantitative methods.

This plan will be used as a monitoring tool to measure the project's impact on a broader scale by the consortium partners and readjust the platform's design if certain indicators are far from being achieved. This report is the initial version of the Impact Assessment Plan, which will be finalized by the end of the project. It involves two main sections. More specifically, after an introduction highlighting the significance and extent of an Impact Assessment Plan, the first part of the document (1.1) outlines the Objectives and Goals of the Plan. This is followed by a description of the methodology (1.2) used to identify the primary dimensions and indicators to be considered for the project's impact assessment and monitoring.

In Chapter 2, we present the key references selected and considered in PreMETS through an initial state-of-the-art desk research focusing on Impact Assessment dimensions and indicators used in other projects and across domains. In section 2.1 the primary dimensions and indicators deemed relevant for PreMETS are illustrated. Then, section 2.2 presents the prioritization exercise that was carried out to select a limited number of indicators, defined as most valuable for PreMETS during the initial stages of the project. Finally, in section 2.4 we provide conclusions and outline future steps for further updating the Plan.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Impact Assessment Plan (IAP) is thought of as a living document that will be updated and revised throughout the whole duration of the PreMETS project, up to M36. To measure and monitor the impact of the PreMETS solution it is vital to choose the right dimensions on which the e-learning platform will most likely have an impact upon and define a set of Indicators that will enable the monitoring of PreMETS on a medium-long term. The definition of the key performance indicators will assist to properly assess how the impact might vary over time in respect to the considered dimensions.

The Impact Assessment Plan (IAP) aims to develop measurement targets and effectively supporting the project activities' implementation. To monitor the indicators, a suite of quantitative and qualitative methods will be used to evaluate the use and impact of PreMETS' solution. The discrepancies between the target values and the values stated during the PreMETS activities will help PreMETS partners align their efforts and implement risk mitigation measures on specific indicators. Hence, the selection of qualitative and quantitative indicators requires an inclusive, consensus-oriented approach to maximize the correct definition, assessment, and monitoring of the project. Therefore, all key stakeholders need to be involved during the indicators' definition, planning, implementation and finally, periodical reviewing processes.

1.1 OBJECTIVES AND GOALS

The goal of an Impact Assessment Plan is to provide a system to measure and monitor different indicators related to the project's exploitation performance, its achievements, and accountability. The assessment begins by redefining the scope and objectives of the developed solution, comprising its targeted group and the desired impact. Establishing clear objectives is important to achieve the main goal set. The objectives can be identified as follows:

1. **Identify and develop indicators:** Establish dimensions and indicators to measure the effectiveness of the PreMETS solution.
2. **Collect data:** Collect pre-assessment data to create a baseline for assessing the impact of PreMETS final solution. After the development of the final solution, this type of data set should be continuously collected to monitor progress. The difference between the initial status and the final one will be reflected in the data, and it will be crucial to identify the changes resulting from the adoption of PreMETS. The methodology should utilize a combination of quantitative and qualitative assessment measures. Quantitative data, such as numerical values and statistics, can help identify trends over a large pool of PreMETS adopters. Qualitative analysis, including surveys and interviews, can provide insights into

individual user experiences and help explore the acceptability of PreMETS solution in a deeper way. Often the two measurements can be combined to better evaluate the solution's impact over the dimensions identified. To collect data, it is necessary to engage primary stakeholders and direct users, as well as secondary that connecting to the solution indirectly. Soliciting feedback on PreMETS can help identify potential barriers and define strategies and mitigations to promptly overcome them. Including different target groups in the impact assessment will be useful to generate a comprehensive and well-rounded impact assessment. Data collection will respect the privacy of PreMETS users and comply with data protection regulations.

- 3. Evaluate changes and monitor impact:** Analysing the collected data will help identify and examine trends in key indicators. Comparing pre- and post-adoption outcomes, considering any other factors that may also influence the results (e.g., changes in legislation, economies, or technological breakthroughs) will highlight the level of impact of the PreMETS solution at the current time. It is necessary to monitor any changes in the data sets using the established performance indicators and/or evaluate those indicators only after the adoption of PreMETS solution. Costs associated to the monitoring of indicators should be identified and weighted against the potential benefits.
- 4. Adapt and refine the solution:** Based on the feedback received and analysed from the evaluation of the collected data, any necessary modifications to the PreMETS solution should be made and adopt countermeasures to reach a certain indicator. Adjusting implementation and exploitation strategies can maximize the solution's impact.

In the following section the methodology adopted to create PreMETS's Impact Assessment Plan will be described in detail.

1.2 Methodology

While both the Impact Assessment and Quality Assessment are important tools for evaluating projects and programs, the two differ in their scope, purpose, focus, timeframe, and the stakeholders involved in the measurements of their impact. The Impact Assessment Plan will be looking at the broader, long-term consequences of PreMETS adoption as a platform, whereas the Quality Assessment assesses the adherence to predefined quality standards and processes throughout the project's lifecycle from the quality indicators perspective. The data collection methods for Impact Assessment and Quality Assessment can overlap in some areas, but also retain significant differences based on their distinct purposes and focus.

The methodological approach undertaken to identify and select the most pertinent dimensions and indicators for measuring the impact of PreMETS solution consisted of three main steps:

- **Step1: State-of-the-Art (SoA)**
This step performed the analysis on dimensions and indicators currently used in e-learning solutions. It included the contribution of the partners as they were requested to send through meaningful materials (e.g., reports, white papers, scientific papers) that could help delineating the dimensions and indicators to be included in the IAP.
- **Step 2: Definition of Dimensions and Indicators**
In this phase a list of indicators for each dimension developed was framed. The importance of dimensions was determined based on the project's goals, objectives, and the interests of key stakeholders. It is often beneficial to engage with stakeholders to prioritize dimensions according to their concerns and interests. Additionally, a comprehensive impact assessment may include other dimensions or sub-dimensions specific to the project's context.
- **Step 3: Consensus Exercise**
In this phase a consensus-building exercise involving the consortium partners was carried out in order to prioritise indicators from the list. In summary, while dimensions coming out of the SoA might seem essential, their relative importance depends on the specific project and its stakeholders: a well-rounded assessment plan considers the unique aspects and goals of the initiative being evaluated, collecting input by each partner of the consortium.

In the following chapter the Impact Assessment Plan development will be articulated through these three steps.

2 IMPACT ASSESSMENT PLAN

The Impact Assessment Plan is a living document that will serve as the basis to start measuring and monitoring defined indicators that will be reiterated and extended based on the project's evolution and proposed PreMETS solution.

2.1 State of the Art (SoA)

To establish the Dimensions and Indicators useful to measure the impact of PreMETS, a preliminary SoA on Dimensions and Indicators was carried out with the primary objective of discerning and prioritizing dimensions for assessing the impact of the PreMETS solution.

To guide our analysis and indicator selection process, the following research questions were framed:

What dimensions are commonly used to measure the impact of solutions similar to the one proposed in PreMETS? How can indicators be developed for these dimensions? What

dimensions and corresponding indicators are deemed most important for our project, and what could their feasibility and measurement efforts be?

The data sources for this research included existing academic literature, case studies of similar projects, and reports from relevant organizations that can be found in Appendix B. The investigation revealed a significant degree of heterogeneity in the field of dimensions to be considered when designing an Impact Assessment Plan, making it challenging to establish a universal gold standard. Moreover, no established impact assessment plans on the topic of e-learning could be found. Consequently, we embarked on a quest to draw inspiration from best practices in various related domains. In this first version of the Impact Assessment Plan, after a first screening of the whole bibliography collected, a couple of sources have been identified as most useful in this preliminary analysis and development of a base line for the advancement of the assessment plan definition. In the following section, we will briefly describe these sources, providing concrete examples that shed light on the most interesting dimensions and indicators that could be also applied to PreMETS.

Dimensions

Social, economic, environmental, and cultural dimensions are often described as necessary elements to be included when conducting an impact assessment. These dimensions are crucial because they help assess the broader and more holistic effects of a project, program, or policy on various aspects of society and the environment. The Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and the Research and Innovation (R&I) Horizon Frameworks should be mentioned as they are pivotal guides for shaping the objectives, methodologies, and impact assessments of research initiatives.

The Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) established in 2000 by world leaders at the United Nations are probably the most famous and exponential example of an outlined shared vision for a better future, which included reducing poverty, hunger, and disease, improving maternal and child health, providing education for all, advancing gender equality, protecting the environment, and fostering global partnerships. The MDGs consisted of eight specific goals, that similar from the concept of the Dimensions used in a IAP, were each supported by 60 indicators, aimed to address critical global challenges and measure and monitor the progress made towards those goals. MDGs, are pivotal in framing global development agendas and continue to provide invaluable insights into addressing pressing societal challenges. While this example is highly known, the concept of dimensions and indicators is adaptable to many different domains, depending on the need of what it needs to be assessed and monitored to advance towards the achievement of predefined targets.

The R&I Horizon framework instead can be considered the best practice showcasing how the monitoring and evaluation for Research & Innovation should be carried out. It was established in 2022 by *The European Commission Directorate for Research and Innovation* (Nixon, 2022). The three considered dimensions are: Scientific, Societal and Economic & Technological.

Beyond these two core frameworks, other notable frameworks that have emerged from the wealth of experience in diverse research domains offer unique perspectives and invaluable insights. These additional frameworks, while not the central focus of our discussion, provide supplementary viewpoints that enrich the tapestry of research methodologies and practices to be taken into consideration when developing a IAP, as well as offering valuable considerations to make when defining the dimensions to monitor throughout a project.

For example, from a paper published by Fraunhofer ISI discussing the topic of “societal impacts”, it emerged that there is a distinction to be drawn between the so-called “Social Impacts” and “Societal Impacts” (Burher et al, 2022). While “social impacts” are often associated with individual and community well-being and experiences, “societal impacts” have a more extensive scope, considering the broader implications and contributions to society as they already include within them the economic, cultural, and policy-related dimensions (Ibid., p.2). It is important to note that these distinctions may vary in different contexts and interpretations, and the use of these terms can be somewhat fluid, although, to represent both. Having in mind this distinction, we opted for a “societal dimension” to be assessed and monitored throughout PreMETS. As e-learning platforms can facilitate the formation of online learning communities, assessing the platform's ability to foster collaboration, peer-to-peer interaction, and the exchange of knowledge among learners can gauge its impact on social capital. Higher levels of social interaction and engagement can indicate a positive impact on building social networks within the learning community.

Another useful framework in a R&I project funded by the EU Union within the Horizon2020 Framework and considered in the SoA is “SoPHIA: Social Platform for Holistic Heritage Impact Assessment Impact Assessment” (SoPHIA D2.3, 2021). SoPHIA strives to enhance the evaluation of European historical environments and cultural heritage interventions. To do so, it seeks out best practices, introduces a comprehensive impact assessment model (tested through case studies), and aims to create policy briefs and recommendations for future European endeavours. SoPHIA's assessment framework is divided into themes (what we consider domains) and sub-themes. Sub-themes are measured through a series of indicators that can be of quantitative or qualitative nature. Hence, in other words, each dimension includes a description of specific issues that must be considered under their sub-dimension to assess the intervention.

Whilst the cultural heritage is far from the manufacturing domain and from PreMETS solution, the assessment model developed for SoPHIA informed the decision of including dimensions and sub-dimensions to break down the different aspects to take into consideration. Moreover, alongside the Societal dimension (in SoPHIA addressed as Social Capital) in SoPHIA's framework the Governance dimension informed the decision to add the Governance dimension in PreMETS's IAP. Assessing the e-learning platform's reliability, credibility, and its commitment to providing quality education while adhering to ethical, legal, and regulatory standards is significant: the more the e-learning platform is well-governed and the more it is likely to be effective and trustworthy for users and stakeholders, impacting also Policy Making (at a local, national and international Level including EU) and cross-sectorial investments dedicated to PM.

Other relevant reports and papers informed this document and while they are not in detail explicated here, they are all listed in Annex A.

Indicators

Different sources underline the importance of a systematic approach to indicator development, considering factors such as their relevance, feasibility, and alignment with policy goals (Gouédard, 2021; Ilham et al., 2022). While these findings can be generalized to various fields, emphasizing the need for a thoughtful and context-specific approach to indicator selection is necessary to support effective assessment and monitoring. The underscore of the role of indicators in enhancing decision-making processes and policy implementation was considered valuable and inserted in the Plan as a measure of impact as well. Indicators should be "S-M-A-R-T" which stands for:

- **Specific:** Indicators should be crystal clear, focusing on who is doing what and how. The data collected should directly relate to the objective without any confusion.
- **Measurable:** If an indicator cannot be measured progress cannot be tracked down. Hence, once the indicator is clear and specific, it becomes measurable in various ways.
- **Achievable:** The indicator should reflect realistic changes that can be linked to the intervention. It should also have achievable performance targets.
- **Relevant:** The indicators should be a valid measure of the outcome and should be backed by research and expertise. It should align with the theories behind the project
- **Timely:** The indicators need to be timely in terms of data collection, reflecting the resources available. They should also match the timing of the outcome changes and impact.

SMART indicators can help track progress effectively and ensure that everyone understands what's being measured and why (Gouédard, 2021). It must be kept in mind that a logical system, where

different indicators contribute to producing an overall understanding of the different dimensions might influence the achievement of desired outcomes.

When defining the indicators for PreMETS, we referred to the consortium and the SoA. Specifically related to education, particular highlight was directed to the OECD who yearly publishes the Indicators of Education Systems (INES) named *Education at a Glance*. The publication comprehends a rich list of indicators that reached a consensus among professionals on how to measure the current state of education internationally in order to inform policy making. Indicator systems such as INES allow to compare educational systems across different countries and across time. Four main categories are differentiating the list of indicators: i) output and outcomes of education; ii) access, participation, and progress in education; iii) resources invested in education, and iv) teaching workforce and learning environment (Gouëdard, 2021, p.13). The categories identified by OECD helped keeping in mind the indicators that would have been relevant for PreMETS solution, considering the same categories. An Indicator to be considered well and fully defined should be provided with the following information:

1. Title
2. Definition
3. Purpose
4. Rationale
5. Method of measurement

The method of measurement should be comprehensive of the data collection method to be used to gather the relevant data, and the measurement tool used to calculate the indicators (UNAIDS, 2010).

2.2 Definition of dimensions and indicators

Based on the SoA, a number of Dimensions were considered as most important, namely the societal dimension, the governance dimension the environmental dimension and the economic dimension. For each dimension, a set of themes, as illustrated in *Table 1*, were identified as most interested to the project and significant for the first version of the IAP. The dimensions' boundaries are sometimes blurred and not always definite. Hence, certain themes developed in one dimension might be relevant or might influence as a result another dimension.

Table 1. Impact dimensions and related themes identified through the SoA

Impact Dimensions	Themes
<p>SOCIETAL</p> <p>Considers the impact that PreMETS has on its learners, as well as other users considered as potential targets of interest</p>	<p>Acceptability</p> <p>Learning experience</p> <p>Accessibility</p> <p>Local & Regional Engagement</p> <p>National, transnational, European and international Engagement</p> <p>Adoption</p> <p>Collaboration</p>
<p>GOVERNANCE</p> <p>Considers whether institutions are able to use PreMETS to partially overcome potential differences in social capital, through their good governance as well as cross-sectorial cooperation and partnerships.</p>	<p>Regional funds and investments in PM</p> <p>Policy Making</p> <p>Inclusivity</p>
<p>ENVIRONMENTAL</p> <p>Considers whether PreMETS does directly or indirectly contribute to enhance an healthy relationship with the earth and its resources and establish more sustainable behaviours in its users.</p>	<p>Awareness</p> <p>Sustainability</p>
<p>ECONOMIC</p> <p>Considers whether industries adopting PreMETS change their employability, income, operating costs, productivity and competitiveness over time.</p>	<p>Efficiency</p> <p>Upskilling and employability</p>

As it was not immediately found an established consensus on what is the right framework to be used in the Impact Assessment Plan for e-learning solutions, the dimensions chosen were used to generate a first set of indicators and their measurements, including 42 indicators -non homogeneously spread across the four dimensions. To be able to prioritize a list of selected indicators, partners engaged in a prioritization exercise that will be described in section 2.3.

2.3 Dimensions and Indicators prioritization exercise

The consortium partners played a central role in the selection process for defining and selecting a preliminary list of indicators of the first version of the Impact Assessment Plan. A structured voting process was conducted among consortium partners to determine a consensus on the indicators for

each dimension. Each partner was asked to independently rank each indicator (on a Likert scale from 1 to 5) based on three variables:

- **Importance for the Project:** The extent to which the indicator aligns with the project's goals and objectives (from 1 “Not relevant” to 5 “High relevance”)
- **Feasibility:** The practicality and ease of data collection and measurement for each indicator (from 1 “Unfeasible” to 5 “Highly feasible”).
- **Effort Needed:** The resources, time, and effort required to measure the indicator effectively (from 1 “None” to 5 “High”).

Moreover, partners were asked to provide feedback and suggestions on the methods illustrated as potential methods to be used in the assessment and the targets to be set to measure each indicator.

The data collected from the consortium partners' evaluations were analyzed to identify dimensions and indicators that received higher consensus scores across the three variables and conclude on a preliminary list of key performance indicators and metrics. The average value of the resulting score across the different voting actors was calculated to allow prioritization. In the analysis, priority was given to those indicators reaching a high score (4 or 5) under the “relevance to the project” category, followed by a high score in their “feasibility” category and favoring expected low expenditure of resources and effort. These indicators and the related dimensions were subsequently prioritized to be included as main impact measurement elements in the project. In the following table an overview of the indicators that were selected is provided. The full list of indicators, and the average ranking that was calculated after the assessment of the consortium voting is illustrated in Annex B.

2.3 Prioritised list of dimensions and indicators

This section presents the final list of dimensions and indicators, as obtained after the prioritization exercise.

Table 2. Final List of Dimensions and Indicators.

Impact Dimensions	Themes	Indicators		Base	Target	Measurement unit	Method	How
SOCIETAL Considers the impact that PreMETS has on its learners, as well as other users considered as potential targets of interest	Acceptability	% of trustworthiness in e-learning platforms	Is the users' trust and acceptance of technologies increased by the active usage of PreMETS?	after- pre assessment	>45%	1-5 scale index and/or subjective reflections	Quanti/Qualitative	Perceptions survey with regards to learner's trust of e-learning plaforms pre and after the use of PreMETS and semi-structured interviews with a pool of chosen users based on their different background
		% of interest in e-learning platforms	Is the interest for e-elarning platform solutions increased?	after- pre assessment	>20%	1-5 scale index	Quantitative	Perceptions survey
	Learning experience	# of trained learners in PM	How many users are trained on PM that before were not?	Initial questions on PM knowledge	1000	Number of registrations	Quantitative	Record/Log Keeping
		# of certified learners via microcredentials	How many users enrolled have successfully completed the modules and are therefore certified via micro-credentials?	0	500	Number of certifications	Quantitative	Record/Log Keeping
		# of trained trainers in PM	How many users are trained on PM that will train other learners?	0	250	Number of certifications	Quantitative	Record/Log Keeping
		# of train-the-	How many train-the-trainers	0	8	Number of	Quantitative	Record/Log Keeping

		trainers modules	modules were adopted?			modules		
		Experience satisfaction	What is the overall learner satisfaction with regards to the PreMETS online platform?	0	>85%	1-5 scale index and/or subjective reflections	Quanti/ Qualitative	Perceptions survey with regards to learner satisfaction and semi-structured interviews to a pool of chosen users based on their different background
			How many key roles in the companies involved in the pilots and adopting PreMETS were satisfied with the platform as an upskilling tool?	TBD after pre-assessment	45%	Subjective/personal reflections on key indicators	Quanti/ Qualitative	Perceptions survey with regards to learner satisfaction and semi-structured interviews to a pool of chosen users based on their different background
	How many key roles in industrial companies outside of the project were satisfied with the platform as an upskilling tool?		TBD after pre-assessment	45%	Subjective/personal reflections on key indicators	Quanti/ Qualitative	Perceptions survey with regards to learner satisfaction and semi-structured interviews to a pool of chosen users based on their different background	
	Local & Regional Engagement	# of targets reached through upskilling and learning networks	How many targets did PreMETS reach indirectly by transferring its outputs to upskilling and learning networks?	0	500000	Targets	Quantitative	Web Analytics
		# of website visitors	Are learners actively visiting and engaging with PreMETS modules and activities?	0	5000	# of visitors	Quantitative	Web Analytics
		# of companies engaged	How many companies engaged with PreMETS platform?	0	20	Number of companies	Quantitative	Record/Log Keeping
	Adoption	# universities and VET centres adopting PreMETS	How many Universities and VET centers did uptake PreMETS platform?	0	50	Number of institutions	Quantitative	Record/Log Keeping

			How many Universities and VET centers with a related PM curricula did uptake PreMETS platform?	50	20%	Number of institutions	Quantitative	Survey
		Assessment of the fitness of PreMETS as an upskilling tool by key roles in companies involved in the pilots adopting the platform	How many external industries were satisfied with in the adoption of PreMETS?	TBD after pre-assessment	45%	Subjective/personal reflections on key indicators	Quanti/Qualitative	Survey that could be followed by semi-structured interviews to know more about the satisfaction of the service offered
ECONOMIC Considers whether industries adopting PreMETS change their employability, income, operating costs, productivity and competitiveness over time.	Upskilling and employability	# of new skills and competencies gained through PreMETS modules	Which are the skills and new competencies gained by certified participants through PreMETS modules?	TBD after pre-assessment	TBD		Quanti/Qualitative	Survey that could be followed by semi-structured interviews
		# Learners able to define and structure their own learning path	Are learners that completed the PreMETS modules able to structure future learning paths?	TBD after pre-assessment	30% increase	Subjective/personal reflections on key indicators	Quanti/Qualitative	Survey that could be followed by semi-structured interviews

2.4 Conclusions and next steps

This chapter outlines the methodology utilized in the SoA analysis and the subsequent definition of dimensions and indicators, as well as the indicator's prioritization process. The active involvement of consortium partners in the task ensured that the selected dimensions and indicators align with the project's goals while also being feasible to measure. As a next step, a preliminary assessment of the indicators to be reviewed and updated during the project evolution will be carried out. This process will be iterative as it will be considering the advances and outcomes of PreMETS solutions. The indicators will be used to monitor and assess the progress of the project. At the end of the project, it will be delivered a final assessment of the indicators.

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ANNEX B: LIST OF INDICATORS

The table below reports the full list of dimensions and indicators, and the assessment provided by PreMETS partners on the relevance feasibility, expenditure of resources/effort. The average assessment value is reported in the table.

Impact Dimensions	Themes	Indicators		Base	Target	Measurement unit	Method	How	RELEVANCE FOR THE PROJECT Not relevant= 1 Low relevance= 2 Relevant=3 Medium Relevance= 4 High Relevance= 5	FEASIBILITY Unfeasible= 1 Low feasibility= 2 Feasible= 3 Medium Feasibility= 4 Highly feasible= 5	EXPENDITURE OF RESOURCES/ EFFORT None= 1 Low = 2 Neutral=3 Medium= 4 High= 5
SOCIETAL Considers the impact that PreMETS has on its learners, as well as other users considered as potential targets of interest	Acceptability	% of trustworthiness in e-learning platforms	Is the users' trust and acceptance of technologies increased by the active usage of PreMETS?	after-pre assessment	>45%	1-5 scale index and/or subjective reflections	Quanti/Qualitative	Perceptions survey with regards to learner's trust of e-learning platforms pre and after the use of PreMETS and semi-structured interviews with a pool of chosen users based on their different background	4	4	3
		% of interest in e-learning platforms	Is the interest for e-learning platform solutions increased?	after-pre assessment	>20%	1-5 scale index	Quantitative	Perceptions survey	4	4	3
	Learning experience	# of trained learners in PM	How many users are trained on PM that before were not?	Initial questions on PM knowledge	1000	Number of registrations	Quantitative	Record/Log Keeping	5	4.5	2

		# of certified learners via microcredentials	How many users enrolled have successfully completed the modules and are therefore certified via micro-credentials?	0	500	Number of certifications	Quantitative	Record/Log Keeping	5	5	2
		# of trained trainers in PM	How many users are trained on PM that will train other learners?	0	250	Number of certifications	Quantitative	Record/Log Keeping	5	4.5	2
		# of train-the-trainers modules	How many train-the-trainers modules were adopted?	0	8	Number of modules	Quantitative	Record/Log Keeping	4.5	4.5	3.5
		# of PM modules developed and integrated into VET curricula	How many PM developed modules were integrated into VET curricula?	0	6	Number of modules	Quantitative	Complete learning pack developed	5	3.5	3.5
		# of PM modules developed and integrated into Universities curricula	How many PM developed modules were integrated into university curricula?	0	6	Number of modules	Quantitative	Complete learning pack developed	4	3.5	3.5
		# of learners that improved the overall ability to think entrepreneurially	How many learners after the completion of PreMETS modules started training their trainers and shaping their training institutions to offer education in a more innovative and entrepreneurial manner?	0%	20%	Percentage	Quanti/ Qualitative	HEINNOVATE tool within the group/faculties that run PreMETS programmes (<i>p. 30 in the GA</i>)	4	3	3
		% of Digital Competencies	Are digital competences of the users engaging with PreMETS increased?	after-pre assessment	20%	1-5 point scale for DigComp	Quantitative	Self-assessed DigComp survey (pre and post training)	4.5	3	3

	Experience satisfaction	What is the overall learner satisfaction with regards to the PreMETS online platform?	0	>85%	1-5 scale index and/or subjective reflections	Quanti/ Qualitative	Perceptions survey with regards to learner satisfaction and semi-structured interviews to a pool of chosen users based on their different background	5	5	3
		How many key roles in the companies involved in the pilots and adopting PreMETS were satisfied with the platform as an upskilling tool?	TBD after pre-assessment	45%	Subjective/personal reflections on key indicators	Quanti/ Qualitative	Perceptions survey with regards to learner satisfaction and semi-structured interviews to a pool of chosen users based on their different background	5	5	3
		How many key roles in industrial companies outside of the project were satisfied with the platform as an upskilling tool?	TBD after pre-assessment	45%	Subjective/personal reflections on key indicators	Quanti/ Qualitative	Perceptions survey with regards to learner satisfaction and semi-structured interviews to a pool of chosen users based on their different background	5	5	3
	Accessibility	# of learners with minor or major accessibility issues (e.g., auditory, visibility impairments) that could complete PreMETS modules	Could individuals with minor/major impairments still be able to successfully complete PreMETS modules?	after pre-assessment	all	Y/N	Quantitative	Survey that could be followed by semi-structured interviews to know more about the experience	4	3.5

	Local & Regional Engagement	# of targets reached through upskilling and learning networks	How many targets did PreMETS reach indirectly by transferring its outputs to upskilling and learning networks?	0	500000	Targets	Quantitative	Web Analytics	4.5	3	2
		# of social media engagement/reactions	Are users interested and accessing PreMETS posts and social media platforms?	0	100 000	# of reactions	Quantitative	Web Analytics	3	4	2.5
		# of website visitors	Are learners actively visiting and engaging with PreMETS modules and activities?	0	5000	# of visitors	Quantitative	Web Analytics	4.5	4.5	2
		# of companies engaged	How many companies engaged with PreMETS platform?	0	20	Number of companies	Quantitative	Record/Log Keeping	5	5	3
	National, transnational, European and international Engagement	# meetings with people from EU Pact Skills	The skills achievable through PreMETS where integrated in the EU Pact for skills?	None	Fully	None/Partially/Fully	Quanti/Qualitative	Survey that could be followed by semi-structured interviews to know more about those skills that were considered meaningful for the EUPact and those that were not and why	4	3	4
		# manufacturing learners	How many manufacturing learners will access modules and materials via the PreMETS platform enabling the reuse of existing EU platforms?	0	30 0000	Number of learners	Quantitative	Record/Log Keeping	4	3	3

Adoption			(Considering the Teaching Factory concept of EIT Manufacturing)								
	# of SME's adopting PreMETS	How many SME's will be reached by via the PreMETS network's partners?	0	20 000	Number of SME's	Quantitative	Record/Log Keeping	4	3	3	
	# universities and VET centres adopting PreMETS	How many Universities and VET centers did uptake PreMETS platform?	0	50	Number of institutions	Quantitative	Record/Log Keeping	4.5	4	3	
		How many Universities and VET centers with a related PM curricula did uptake PreMETS platform?	50	20%	Number of institutions	Quantitative	Survey	5	4	4	
	% dropouts in the institutions adopting PreMETS	Could the institutions adopting PreMETS reduce the dropouts by providing and e-learning service?	TBD after pre-assessment	15% decrease within 2y	Percentage	Quantitative	Survey	3	3	4	
	# of industrial stakeholders adopting PreMETS platform for upskilling their employees	How many external stakeholders were interested in the adoption of PreMETS?	0	30	Number of companies	Quantitative	Record/Log Keeping	5	3	3	
	Assessment of the fitness of PreMETS as an upskilling tool by key roles in companies involved in the pilots adopting the platform	How many external industries were satisfied with in the adoption of PreMETS?	TBD after pre-assessment	45%	Subjective/personal reflections on key indicators? ?	Quanti/Qualitative	Survey that could be followed by semi-structured interviews to know more about the satisfaction of the service	4	4	3	

								offered			
	Collaboration	# of developed clusters	How many other projects and learning platforms were interested in PreMETS to develop a cluster of activities and collaborate further?	0	3	Number of collaboration opportunities generated	Quanti/Qualitative	Survey that could be followed by semi-structured interviews to know more about the sort of collaboration established	3	4	4
GOVERNANCE Considers whether institutions were able to use PreMETS to partially overcome potential differences in social capital, through their good governance as well as cross-sectorial cooperation and partnerships.	Regional funds and investments in PM	Amount of funding obtained	Which is the amount of funding obtained to sustain PreMETS exploitation of the platform and its activities?	0	500000 eur	Eur	Quantitative	Combined budget of projects sustaining PreMETS' efforts	3	3	5
	Policy Making	# policy makers interested in PreMETS	Which is the number of policy makers that shows interest in using PreMETS platform for promoting sustainability and industrial resilience?	0	10	Number of policy makers	Quantitative	Record/Log Keeping	3.5	4	3
			Which is the level of interest that policy makers showed towards PreMETS as a viable example to promote sustainability and industrial resilience?	0	3	Levels of interest: awareness (level1), presentation (level 2) and reference (level 3)	Quantitative	Surveys and Policy Reports' analysis	3	4	3.5

	Inclusivity	# of learners that were previously unable to access online education that could access PreMETS	Could individuals that were previously underserved and had difficulties accessing online education able to access PreMETS modules?	after pre-assessment	25% increase within 2y	Percentage	Quantitative	Survey that could be followed by semi-structured interviews	2.5	3	4
		# of learners from social groups at risk involved in the project	Could individuals part of social groups at risk based on economic, cultural, social, geographic, learning difficulties access PM education through PreMETS?	0	300	Number of registrations	Quantitative	Record/Log Keeping of # of learners that could access the platform through a specific fee/	3	2	4
ENVIRONMENTAL Considers whether PreMETS does directly or indirectly contribute to enhance an healthy relationship with the earth and its resources and establish more sustainable behaviours in its users.	Awareness	% of green competencies increase	Are green competencies of the users engaging with PreMETS increased?	after pre assessment	20%	1-5 point scale for GreenComp	Quantitative	Self-assessed GreenComp survey (pre and post training)	2	3	3
	Sustainability	% of Sustainable Behaviours increase	Is PreMETS as an online e-learning platform (if compared to the face to face learning and what it entails), indirectly contributing to increasing more sustainable behaviors?	after pre assessment	TBD		N/A		3	2	4
		# of companies adhering to national/international and social regulations	How many companies that were not yet compliant with national/international environmental and social regulations adhered to the regulation after completing	after pre assessment	TBD		N/A	p.30 in the GA	2	2	4

			PreMETS modules?								
		% hazardous waste	Did the manufacturing companies that engaged with PM in PreMETS downsized costly repairs and unexpected equipment failure?	after-pre assessment	TBD		N/A		3	2	4
		% optimisation of primary resources	Did the manufacturing companies that engaged with PM in PreMETS optimised their primary sources consumption while reducing hazardous waste?	after-pre assessment	17%	Percentage	Quantitative	Life Cycle analysis toolkit (p.30 in the GA)	3	2	4
		% reduction of CO2 and GHG emissions	Did the manufacturing companies that engaged with PM in PreMETS reduced their Co2 and GHG emissions stemming from their operations?	after-pre assessment	7%	Percentage	Quantitative	Life Cycle analysis toolkit (p.30 in the GA)	2.5	2	4
		% of companies' Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	How many companies adopting PM after the use of PreMETS platform could provide a better value for citizens tangent to their physical industrial infrastructures (i.e. those crossing urban areas) boosting their CSR?	0%	40%	Percentage	Quantitative	TBD	2	2	4
ECONOMIC Considers	Efficiency	% of productivity	Did the manufacturing companies that	after-pre assess	18% increase	Percentage	Quantitative	Medium long term	4.5	3	3

<p>whether industries adopting PreMETS change their employability, income, operating costs, productivity and competitiveness over time.</p>	<p>Upskilling and employability</p>		<p>engaged with PM in PreMETS increase their production due to reduced downtime due to disruptions?</p>	ment							
		<p># of new skills and competencies gained through PreMETS modules</p>	<p>Which are the skills and new competencies gained by certified participants through PreMETS modules?</p>	<p>TBD after pre-assessment</p>	<p>TBD</p>		<p>Quanti/Qualitative</p>	<p>Survey that could be followed by semi-structured interviews</p>	<p>5</p>	<p>4</p>	<p>4</p>
		<p># Learners able to define and structure their own learning path</p>	<p>Are learners that completed the PreMETS modules able to structure future learning paths?</p>	<p>TBD after pre-assessment</p>	<p>25% increase</p>	<p>Subjective/personal reflections on key indicators</p>	<p>Quanti/Qualitative</p>	<p>Survey that could be followed by semi-structured interviews</p>	<p>4</p>	<p>4</p>	<p>4</p>
		<p># partnerships established between PreMETS participants and industry stakeholders</p>	<p>How many external industry stakeholders established a partnership with PreMETS participants?</p>	<p>0</p>	<p>TBD</p>	<p>Number of companies</p>	<p>Quantitative</p>	<p>Survey</p>	<p>4</p>	<p>3</p>	<p>3</p>